

Distributed Nash Equilibrium Seeking over Time-Varying Signed Networks

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Abstract—This work extends the distributed Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm to address multi-agent games under time-varying, signed, and undirected communication networks. Initially, based on uniform complete observability for linear time-varying systems, a new analytical framework is developed to determine the necessary and sufficient condition for achieving globally uniformly exponential stability of the error dynamics of the distributed estimator. It is shown that exponential stability is realized if and only if the joint (ϵ, T) -connectivity and the negative-link assumption of time-varying signed graphs are satisfied. Subsequently, it is demonstrated that under some mild conditions, the seeking algorithm ensures the global uniform exponential convergence of players' strategies towards the Nash equilibrium.

Index Terms—Nash equilibrium seeking, time-varying networks, signed networks, multi-agent systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE distributed Nash equilibrium seeking problem over networks, where players exchange information about strategies and cost functions through a communication network, has garnered increased attention in multi-agent games [1], [2]. It has extensive applications in non-cooperative games and has been adapted for cooperative control and optimization problems for multi-agent systems (MAS). Application examples include mobile sensor networks [3], unmanned air vehicle formations [4], satellite clusters [5], and multi-robot coordination [6]. Especially, for the two-network zero-sum game, the distributed convergence to the Nash equilibrium over general communication networks and Nash equilibrium computation over switching communication networks were studied in [7] and [8], respectively. By introducing a leader-follower consensus protocol to the gradient system, researchers investigated a distributed Nash equilibrium seeking strategy over undirected and connected networks in [9], and this strategy was extended to N -coalition non-cooperative games over strongly connected networks in [10], [11].

Additionally, to accommodate the unreliable communication conditions, the distributed Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm proposed

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in [9] was applied to multi-agent games with both strongly connected switching networks and switching networks with occasional loss of communication in [12]. Further extensions were made to jointly connected switching networks in [13], [14]. Also, a distributed discrete-time algorithm for the Nash equilibrium seeking problem over Markovian switching communication networks was proposed in [15]. To improve communication efficiency, the work in [16] introduced a novel stochastic event-triggered algorithm for distributed constrained Nash equilibrium seeking problems. Recently, [17], [18] proposed distributed Nash Equilibrium seeking algorithms over networks with linear convergence rate.

It is noteworthy that the network models discussed above primarily assume the absence of repelling interactions among neighboring agents, as they consider only nonnegative edge weights in graphs. However, in practice, repelling interactions among agents, represented by negative edge weights, are often prevalent in many networked systems [19]. These interactions arise from faulty communication, adversarial attacks, or dynamic perturbations within the communication networks. For example, antagonistic relations in social networks [20], repressive connections in biological regulatory networks [21], and negative reactance or significant angle differences across power system transmission lines [22]. Recently, the authors in [23] proposed a novel coalition game algorithm to address the formulated Nash equilibrium seeking problem for MAS over a static cooperation-competition network, specifically focusing on only the opposing interactions along the negative edges.

Apart from repelling interactions, changes in network interaction relationships and weights over time are common occurrences due to, for example, external attacks, sensor/actuator failures, or changes in the environment [24], [25]. Therefore, considering dynamic cooperative/antagonistic interactions among agents is a significant research topic towards enhancing the systems' capacity to adapt to complex environments. Time-varying signed graphs, that assign positive or negative values to represent the nature of time-varying links, are commonly used to represent dynamic cooperative/antagonistic relationships between connected agents [26]. Such graphs can model a broad range of practical applications. For example, in sensor networks, Sybil attacks, where a malicious node forges multiple identities, can dynamically alter the network topology by creating or removing edges over time. Moreover, if a Sybil attack causes one sensor to mistrust another's data, the edge between them may carry a negative weight, reflecting this adversarial relationship [27]. However, to the best of our knowledge, *there has been no exploration of time-varying signed weighted communication networks, where negative edges introduce repelling interactions among agents, in the context of Nash equilibrium seeking problems.*

This work significantly extends the distributed Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm proposed in [9], consisting of pseudogradient dynamics and a distributed estimator based on the leader-follower consensus protocol, to address multi-agent games with time-varying signed communication networks. This work faces two challenges: firstly, the presence of negative edges violates fundamental properties

of the conventional Laplacian matrix that commonly used in consensus analysis of multi-agent systems. For example, signed Laplacians may be indefinite, and the connectivity of the graph no longer guarantees that the Laplacian has corank 1. Hence, the existing network connectivity conditions become ineffective for enabling each player to accurately estimate the strategies of others, ultimately resulting in the failure to converge to the Nash equilibrium. Secondly, the time-varying signed interactions in communication networks invalidate the applicability of conventional Lyapunov-based analysis, which is commonly employed in existing distributed Nash equilibrium seeking problems.

To overcome the aforementioned challenges, this work focuses on the essence of the influence of time-varying signed weights on consensus protocol and introduces new requirements for the network graphs to accommodate this influence. Moreover, it develops a novel analytical framework based on the complete observability theory [29]-[31] to ensure the stability of the distributed estimator. The main contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- This paper focuses on a non-cooperative game problem formulated within the time-varying signed networks for multi-agent systems, where the negative edges represent repelling interactions. These interactions are distinguished from the opposing interactions discussed in [23] due to their unique characteristics and differing dynamic definitions. Utilizing a necessary and sufficient result derived from the theory of uniform complete observability for linear time-varying systems, exponential stability is achieved for the error dynamics of the proposed distributed estimator if and only if the time-varying signed communication networks satisfy the joint (ϵ, T) -connectivity and the negative-link assumptions. This result is crucial for the Lyapunov analysis of the extended distributed Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm.
- Under some mild conditions, the extended distributed Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm based on time-varying signed graphs is proven to achieve the global uniform exponential convergence of players' strategies towards the Nash equilibrium.

The structure of the remaining paper is as follows: Section II provides an overview of the preliminaries and formulates the problem under consideration. Section III presents the primary result of this work, detailing the Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm, the key lemmas required for Lyapunov analysis, and the corresponding convergence results. Section IV provides a numerical example to illustrate the key findings. Finally, concluding remarks are provided in Section V.

Notations. Let \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{R}_+ denote the set of real numbers and non-negative real numbers, respectively, \mathbb{Z} and \mathbb{Z}_+ denote the set of integers and non-negative integers, respectively, and \mathbb{R}^n and $\mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ denote the n -dimensional and $n \times m$ -dimensional real spaces equipped with the Euclidean norm $\|\cdot\|$, respectively. Further, I_n denotes the n -dimensional identity matrices, $\mathbf{1}_n$ (or $\mathbf{0}_n$) denotes an n -dimensional column vector with all the elements being 1 (or 0), and $\lambda(H)$ the eigenvalue for matrix H . The maximum and minimum eigenvalues for matrix H are denoted by $\lambda_{\max}(H)$ and $\lambda_{\min}(H)$, respectively. Denote the spectral radius of a square matrix A by $\rho(A)$. $A = \text{diag}\{a_i, i = 1, \dots, N\}$ denotes a diagonal matrix with diagonal elements a_1, a_2, \dots, a_N and $B = \text{diag}\{b_{ij}, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N\}$ denotes a diagonal matrix whose diagonal elements are $b_{11}, b_{12}, \dots, b_{1N}, b_{21}, \dots, b_{2N}, \dots, b_{NN}$. The Moore-Penrose pseudoinverse of matrix Π is denoted by Π^\dagger . Finally, \otimes denotes the Kronecker product.

II. PRELIMINARIES AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

Prior to presenting the main results of this work, a concise overview of foundational concepts relevant to this work is provided below.

A. Signed Weighted Undirected Interaction Graph

An undirected time-varying graph $\mathcal{G}(t) = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}(t), \mathcal{A}(t))$ is used to model the time-varying communication topology of a multi-agent system (MAS), where $\mathcal{V} := \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ is the node set of MAS, $\mathcal{E}(t) \subseteq \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V}$ is the edge set, and $\mathcal{A}(t) := [a_{ij}(t)] \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ is a weighted symmetric adjacency matrix. The edge weight $a_{ij}(t)$ associated with edge $(j, i) \in \mathcal{E}(t)$ can be positive, 0, or negative. $a_{ij}(t) > 0$ indicates a cooperative interaction between player i and its neighbor j . Conversely, $a_{ij}(t) < 0$ indicates a repelling interaction between them. $a_{ij}(t) = 0$ indicates that agent j can not directly access the information of agent i . Additionally, $a_{ii}(t) = 0, i \in \mathcal{V}$. The Laplacian matrix of graph $\mathcal{G}(t)$ is denoted by $L(t) := [l_{ij}(t)] \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ with $l_{ii}(t) = \sum_{j=1}^N a_{ij}(t)$ and $l_{ij}(t) = -a_{ij}(t)$ if $i \neq j$. A sequence of edges $\{(i_1, i_2), (i_2, i_3), \dots, (i_k, i_{k+1})\}$ is called a path of $\mathcal{G}(t)$ from i_1 to i_{k+1} at time t , and then node i_{k+1} is said to be reachable from node i_1 . An undirected graph is connected if there is a path between any pair of nodes.

For a graph \mathcal{G} with N nodes and m edges, denote by \mathcal{G}_+ (\mathcal{G}_- , respectively) the spanning subgraph of \mathcal{G} with only the positively weighted edges (only the negatively weighted edges, respectively). The graph \mathcal{G} can be expressed as the union of three subgraphs: $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{F}_- \cup \mathcal{C}_- \cup \mathcal{G}_+$, where $\mathcal{F}_- = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{F}_-})$ is a spanning forest of \mathcal{G}_- , and \mathcal{C}_- is a spanning subgraph consisting of the remaining edges in \mathcal{G}_- . Let $D \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times m}$ is a $(-1, 0, 1)$ -matrix whose rows are indexed by the nodes and columns are indexed by the edges, where the (i, k) th entry is 1 if node i is the head of e_k , -1 if node i is the tail of e_k , and 0 otherwise. With a suitable labeling of the edges, the incidence matrix D can be partitioned as: $D = [D_{\mathcal{F}_-}, D_{\mathcal{C}_-}, D_{\mathcal{G}_+}]$.

Assumption 1: $a_{ij}(t)$ are measurable functions for nodes i and j , $i, j \in \mathcal{V}$. Moreover, there exists a constant $a > 0$ such that $|a_{ij}(t)| < a$, for all $i, j \in \mathcal{V}$ and for all $t \geq 0$. \square

Definition 1: (Joint (ϵ, T) -connectivity [29]): The time-varying graph $\mathcal{G}(t)$ is said to be jointly (ϵ, T) -connected if there exist two constants $\epsilon > 0$ and $T > 0$ such that the edges

$$(i, j) : \int_s^{s+T} a_{ij}(t) dt \geq \epsilon, i, j \in \mathcal{V}$$

form a connected graph over the node set \mathcal{V} for all $s \geq 0$. \square

Assumption 2: There exist positive constants $\epsilon > 0$ and $T > 0$ such that graph $\mathcal{G}(t)$ is jointly (ϵ, T) -connected. \square

Remark 1: Assumption 2 ensures the feasibility of information sharing among players through time-varying neighboring communication, thereby facilitating the distributed estimation of their strategies. The connectivity of the graph associated with MAS is not required at all times; rather, what is only required is a condition on constant excitation of the edge weights in a fixed, finite time interval. Note that if all the weights $a_{ij}(t)$, $i, j \in \mathcal{V}$ are nonnegative, the joint (ϵ, T) -connectivity condition is weaker than the switched strongly connected assumption in [12] and the jointly strongly connected assumption in [13]. Moreover, the joint (ϵ, T) -connectivity assumption proposed in [29] can be applied to address the exponential consensus problem for systems when some of the $a_{ij}(t)$ are negative, which inspires our research methods. Therefore, it is applied in this work. \square

B. Game Theory

A game $\mathbf{g} := (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{X}, \mathbf{f})$ is defined by a set of players \mathcal{V} , a set of strategies \mathcal{X} , and a cost function vector \mathbf{f} . For $i \in \mathcal{V}$, player i can choose strategy $x_i \in X_i$, and then the strategies from all players generate the state vector of the game $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X} := X_1 \times X_2 \times \cdots \times X_N$ with $\mathbf{x} := [x_1^T, x_2^T, \cdots, x_N^T]^T$. Correspondingly, the cost function vector $\mathbf{f} := [f_1, f_2, \cdots, f_N]^T$ is composed of players' cost functions $f_i(\mathbf{x})$ or $f_i(x_i, \mathbf{x}_{-i})$, $i \in \mathcal{V}$, where $f_i : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ determines the cost incurred by player i in selecting strategy x_i and $\mathbf{x}_{-i} := [x_1^T, \cdots, x_{i-1}^T, x_{i+1}^T, \cdots, x_N^T]^T$ represents the strategies of all players except player i .

Definition 2: In a N -player non-cooperative differential game, a strategy vector $\mathbf{x}^* := (x_i^*, \mathbf{x}_{-i}^*) \in \mathcal{X}$ is said to be a Nash equilibrium solution if for $x_i^* \in X_i$,

$$f_i(x_i^*, \mathbf{x}_{-i}^*) \leq f_i(x_i, \mathbf{x}_{-i}^*), \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}. \quad \square$$

C. Problem Formulation

Consider a non-cooperative game involving N agents (players) operating within a time-varying signed graph $\{\mathcal{G}(t)\}_{t \geq 0}$, that satisfies Assumptions 1 and 2 and acts as the communication network among agents. Consider the case where player i 's strategy set satisfies $X_i = \mathbb{R}^{n_i}$. Then player i 's strategy evolution is expressed as a dynamic system:

$$\dot{x}_i = u_i, \quad (1)$$

where $i \in \mathcal{V}$, $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i}$ is the strategy of player i , and $u_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i}$ is the control input of player i . Each player i has a cost function $f_i(\mathbf{x})$, where $\mathbf{x} = [x_1^T, x_2^T, \cdots, x_N^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with $n = n_1 + n_2 + \cdots + n_N$. All players contribute to the minimization of their individual cost functions by adjusting their strategies, as given below:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{x_i} f_i(\mathbf{x}) \\ & \text{subject to (1)}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

This work aims to address the game problem above (2) under time-varying signed communication networks, specifically focusing on finding the unique Nash equilibrium using an extension of the distributed Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm proposed in [9] and ensuring its convergence.

Remark 2: Compared to reference [23], which studied Nash equilibrium seeking for linear MAS over signed communication networks with ‘‘opposing interactions’’ along the negative edges, this work focuses on a different interaction type, namely ‘‘repelling interactions’’ along negative edges. In [23], negative edges indicate attraction to the opposite values of neighboring nodes, leading to coalition formation under structural balance. In contrast, this work considers negative edges as repelling forces that drive agents away from the relative positions of their neighbors, a phenomenon often arising from faulty communication or adversarial attacks. Given the distinct characteristics and dynamic properties of repelling interactions, this study introduces appropriate constraints on time-varying signed graphs to mitigate the effects of negative edges and ensure the stability of the distributed estimator within the Nash equilibrium seeking strategy. \square

Define $F(\mathbf{x}) := [(\frac{\partial f_1(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1})^T, (\frac{\partial f_2(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2})^T, \cdots, (\frac{\partial f_N(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_N})^T]^T$ as the pseudogradient vector of \mathbf{f} . For $i \in \mathcal{V}$, define the gradient dynamics

$$\dot{x}_i = -\nabla_i f_i(\mathbf{x}), \quad (3)$$

where $\nabla_i f_i(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\partial f_i(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_i}$. Such gradient dynamics provide the core idea of the distributed Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm. The following assumptions are utilized in the subsequent analysis.

Assumption 3: For each $i \in \mathcal{V}$, function $f_i(\cdot)$ is twice continuously differentiable, and its gradient dynamics $\frac{\partial f_i(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_i}$ is globally m_i -Lipschitz, i.e., there exists a constant $m_i > 0$ such that $\|\frac{\partial f_i(\mathbf{x}_1)}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial f_i(\mathbf{x}_2)}{\partial x_i}\| \leq m_i \|\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2\|$, $\forall \mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^n$. \square

Assumption 4: The pseudogradient vector $F(\mathbf{x})$ is strongly monotone on \mathbb{R}^n with constant $\gamma > 0$, i.e., $(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2)^T (F(\mathbf{x}_1) - F(\mathbf{x}_2)) \geq \gamma \|\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2\|^2$, $\forall \mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^n$. \square

Remark 3: Based on Assumption 3, it is deduced that the pseudogradient $F(\cdot)$ is M -Lipschitz, where $M = (m_1^2 + m_2^2 + \cdots + m_N^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$. This assumption is instrumental in achieving global results. Assumption 4 guarantees the existence and uniqueness of the Nash equilibrium \mathbf{x}^* , satisfying $F(\mathbf{x}^*) = 0$. Furthermore, the combination of Assumptions 3 and 4, along with the gradient dynamics described in equation (3), ensures the global exponential stability of the Nash equilibrium. \square

III. MAIN RESULTS

This section provides the extended distributed Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm to address the game problem (2) formulated in the last section, and then performs its convergence analysis based on three preliminary lemmas.

In the context of time-varying signed graphs, we provide an extension of the distributed Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm proposed in [9] for multi-agent games, which incorporates gradient dynamics and a distributed estimator:

$$u_i = -\zeta \bar{k}_i \frac{\partial f_i}{\partial x_i}(\mathbf{y}_i), \quad (4a)$$

$$\dot{y}_{ij} = -\left(\sum_{l=1}^N a_{il}(t)(y_{ij} - y_{lj}) + a_{ij}(t)(y_{ij} - x_j) \right), \quad (4b)$$

where $i \in \mathcal{V}$, $\mathbf{y}_i = [y_{i1}^T, y_{i2}^T, \cdots, y_{iN}^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes player i 's estimates on all players, $y_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_j}$ denotes player i 's estimate on player j 's strategy, $\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial x_i}(\mathbf{y}_i)$ represents $\frac{\partial f_i(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_i}|_{\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{y}_i}$, ζ is a small positive parameter, \bar{k}_i is a positive fixed parameter, and $a_{ij}(t)$ is the (i, j) th element of the time-varying signed weighted adjacency matrix $\{\mathcal{A}(t)\}_{t \geq 0}$ of graph $\mathcal{G}(t)$. The compact form of (4a)-(4b) is as follows:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = -\zeta \bar{\mathbf{k}} \Theta(\mathbf{y}), \quad (5a)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{y}} = -((L(t) \otimes I_n + B(t))\mathbf{y} - B(t)(\mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x})), \quad (5b)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{k}} = \text{diag}\{\bar{k}_i I_{n_i}\}$, $\mathbf{y} = [y_1^T, y_2^T, \cdots, y_N^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{Nn}$, $\Theta(\mathbf{y}) = [(\frac{\partial f_1(\mathbf{y}_1)}{\partial x_1})^T, (\frac{\partial f_2(\mathbf{y}_2)}{\partial x_2})^T, \cdots, (\frac{\partial f_N(\mathbf{y}_N)}{\partial x_N})^T]^T$, $B(t) = \text{diag}\{a_{ij}(t)I_{n_j}\}$.

A. Exponential Stability Analysis for Distributed Estimator

The four lemmas below first present an application of the uniformly complete observability theory for linear time-varying systems. Under suitably imposed constraints on the graph's negative edge weights and connectivity, the application is then utilized to prove the exponential stability of the error dynamics related to the distributed estimator (5b) over time-varying signed networks, and finally to provide an alternative to the algebraic Lyapunov equation for convergence analysis of the Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm.

Lemma 1: [32] Consider a linear time-varying system

$$\dot{x}(t) = -W(t)W^T(t)x(t), \quad (6)$$

where $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $W(\cdot)$ is a piecewise continuous and almost everywhere bounded matrix mapping function from \mathbb{R}_+ to $\mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$. Let $\Phi(t, s)$ be the state transition matrix of the system shown in (6). This system is globally uniformly exponentially stable in the sense that

there exist $\gamma_1 > 0$, $\gamma_2 > 0$ such that $\|\Phi(t, t_0)\| \leq \gamma_1 e^{-\gamma_2(t-t_0)}$ for all $t \geq t_0$, if and only if there exist some constants $\alpha_1 > 0$, $\alpha_2 > 0$, and $\xi > 0$, such that

$$\alpha_1 I \leq \int_s^{s+\xi} W(t)W^T(t)dt \leq \alpha_2 I \quad (7)$$

holds for all $s \geq t_0$. \square

Let $\Lambda(t) := -(L(t) \otimes I_n + B(t))$ and consider the following linear time-varying system:

$$\dot{\mathbf{y}}(t) = \Lambda(t)\mathbf{y}(t). \quad (8)$$

For each $h = 1, 2, \dots, N$, define a new vector $\bar{\mathbf{y}}_h := [y_{1h}^T, y_{2h}^T, \dots, y_{Nh}^T]^T$ and $\Delta^h(t) := \text{diag} \{a_{lh}(t), l = 1, 2, \dots, N\}$. Then, an equivalent representation of system (8) is given as follows:

$$\dot{\bar{\mathbf{y}}}_h = -(\Pi^h(t) \otimes I_{n_h})\bar{\mathbf{y}}_h, \quad h = 1, 2, \dots, N, \quad (9)$$

where $\Pi^h(t) := L(t) + \Delta^h(t)$. Note that the origin of system (8) is globally uniformly exponentially stable if and only if (9) is globally uniformly exponentially stable for $h = 1, 2, \dots, N$. Matrix $\Pi^h(t)$ can be reflected in the Laplacian matrix of an augmented time-varying signed graph $\hat{\mathcal{G}}^h(t) = (\hat{\mathcal{V}}, \hat{\mathcal{E}}^h(t), \hat{\mathcal{A}}^h(t))$ for each $h = 1, 2, \dots, N$, where $\hat{\mathcal{V}} := 0 \cup \mathcal{V}$, $\hat{\mathcal{E}}^h(t) := \mathcal{E}(t) \cup \mathcal{E}^h(t)$, and $\hat{\mathcal{A}}^h(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+1) \times (N+1)}$, with $\mathcal{E}^h(t) := \{(0, l) | a_{lh}(t) \neq 0, l = 1, 2, \dots, N\}$. It can be seen that

$$\hat{L}^h(t) := \left[\begin{array}{c|c} \mathbf{1}_N^T \Delta^h(t) \mathbf{1}_N & -\mathbf{1}_N^T \Delta^h(t) \\ \hline -\Delta^h(t) \mathbf{1}_N & \Pi^h(t) \end{array} \right] \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+1) \times (N+1)}$$

is the Laplacian of $\hat{\mathcal{G}}^h(t)$. When focusing on the effect of the negative spanning forest $\hat{\mathcal{F}}_-^h(t)$ of the graph $\hat{\mathcal{G}}^h(t)$, the matrix

$$\Gamma_{\hat{\mathcal{F}}_-^h}^h(t) := (D_{\hat{\mathcal{F}}_-^h}^h(t))^T (\hat{L}^h(t))^\dagger D_{\hat{\mathcal{F}}_-^h}^h(t) \quad (10)$$

is defined to capture the influence of negative edge weights in the signed graph.

Assumption 5: (Negative-link assumption) The effect of negative edge weights on the network, characterized by the matrix $\Gamma_{\hat{\mathcal{F}}_-^h}^h(t)$ defined in (10), satisfies $\Gamma_{\hat{\mathcal{F}}_-^h}^h(t) > 0$ for all $t \geq 0$ and for all $h = 1, 2, \dots, N$. \square

Remark 4: Note that the matrix $\Pi^h(t)$ is a loopy signed Laplacian matrix, where each element in the diagonal matrix $\Delta^h(t)$ serves as the weight l_{ii} associated with the self-loop edge [35]. The signed Laplacian matrix $\hat{L}^h(t)$ of $\hat{\mathcal{G}}^h(t)$ provides a representation of $\Pi^h(t)$ as a conventional loop-less Laplacian, which can be utilized to analyze the positive semi-definiteness of $\Pi^h(t)$. In addition, Assumption 5 can be verified in a distributed manner. Relevant results on distributed computation can be found in [36]. \square

Lemma 2: Suppose that Assumption 5 is satisfied. Then, the matrix $\Pi^h(t)$ is positive semi-definite for all $t \geq 0$ and for all $h = 1, 2, \dots, N$. \square

Proof: According to the connection between graph algebra theory and the passivity theory of electrical networks. Each edge of a signed graph can be associated with a resistor whose conductance is defined by the corresponding edge weight (see detailed discussions in reference [19]). The analysis proceeds by considering the following two cases:

- *Case 1.* The graph $\mathcal{G}^h(t)$ is connected at time t . Based on the matrix $\Pi^h(t)$, construct the augmented graph $\hat{\mathcal{G}}^h(t)$. According to the definition of $\Delta^h(t)$, there exists at least one $1 \leq l \leq N$, $l \neq h$, such that $a_{lh}(t) \neq 0$, i.e., there is at least one edge from the node 0 to some node l in the graph $\hat{\mathcal{G}}^h(t)$. Hence, $\hat{\mathcal{G}}^h(t)$ is connected. Together with Assumption 5, it follows from Theorem 1 in [37] that the matrix $\hat{L}^h(t)$ is positive semi-definite.

Furthermore, by Theorem 2 in reference [35], $\Pi^h(t)$ is positive semi-definite.

- *Case 2.* The graph $\mathcal{G}^h(t)$ is not connected at time t . Assume that $\mathcal{G}^h(t)$ consists of q connected components $(\mathcal{G}^h)^{(k)}(t)$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, q$. Accordingly, the matrix $\Pi^h(t)$ can be expressed in a block-diagonal form, where each diagonal block corresponds to a component and is denoted by $(\Pi^h)^{(k)}(t)$. Construct the graph $(\hat{\mathcal{G}}^h)^{(k)}(t)$ for $(\Pi^h)^{(k)}(t)$. If there exist negative edges within the component $(\hat{\mathcal{G}}^h)^{(k)}(t)$, the effect of negative edge weights can be characterized by the matrix $(\Gamma_{\hat{\mathcal{F}}_-^h}^h)^{(k)}(t)$. It is straightforward to observe that $(\Gamma_{\hat{\mathcal{F}}_-^h}^h)^{(k)}(t)$ corresponds to one block of $\Gamma_{\hat{\mathcal{F}}_-^h}^h(t)$. Moreover, Assumption 5 ensures that each block $(\Gamma_{\hat{\mathcal{F}}_-^h}^h)^{(k)}(t) > 0$. Applying the same proof as in *Case 1* to the connected component leads to the conclusion that the loopy signed Laplacian matrix $(\Pi^h(t))^{(k)}(t)$ is positive semi-definite. If all edge weights within a component are nonnegative, the loopy Laplacian matrix $(\Pi^h(t))^{(k)}$ of that component is trivially positive definite. It follows that $\Pi^h(t)$ is positive semi-definite.

In conclusion, $\Pi^h(t)$ is positive semi-definite for all $t \geq 0$ and for all $h = 1, 2, \dots, N$. This completes the proof. \blacksquare

The following lemma presents a necessary and sufficient condition for the exponential stability of system (8) under time-varying signed graphs, which is crucial for obtaining the Lyapunov function candidate for the Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm (5a)-(5b).

Lemma 3: Suppose that the time-varying signed graph $\mathcal{G}(t)$ satisfies Assumptions 1 and 5. The origin of the time-varying linear system (8) is globally uniformly exponentially stable if and only if $\mathcal{G}(t)$ satisfies Assumption 2. \square

Proof: According to Assumption 5 and Lemma 2, $\Pi^h(t)$ is symmetric positive semi-definite for all $t \geq 0$ and for all $h = 1, 2, \dots, N$. For each $h = 1, 2, \dots, N$, construct $W(t) := (\Pi^h(t) \otimes I_{n_h})^{\frac{1}{2}}$ so that system (9) can be re-written into the form of (6) [33]:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\bar{\mathbf{y}}}_h &= -\left[((\Pi^h(t))^{\frac{1}{2}} (\Pi^h(t))^{\frac{1}{2}}) \otimes I_{n_h} \right] \bar{\mathbf{y}}_h \\ &= -\left[(\Pi^h(t) \otimes I_{n_h})^{\frac{1}{2}} (\Pi^h(t) \otimes I_{n_h})^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \bar{\mathbf{y}}_h. \end{aligned}$$

(Sufficiency) Suppose that Assumptions 1, 2, and 5 are satisfied, we show that the origin of system (9) is globally uniformly exponentially stable. For all $s \geq t_0$ and all $L(t)$ of (ϵ, T) -connected graph $\mathcal{G}(t)$, the matrices $\int_s^{s+\xi} L(t)dt$ form a compact set in the following set Γ :

$$\Gamma := \{L \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N} \mid L \text{ is symmetric, } l_{ij} \leq 0, i \neq j, L \cdot \mathbf{1}_N = 0\}.$$

We conclude that for all $s \geq 0$, matrices $\int_s^{s+\xi} L(t)dt$ are positive semi-definite and have a simple zero eigenvalue. Furthermore, for each $h = 1, 2, \dots, N$, since graph $\mathcal{G}(t)$ is (ϵ, T) -connected, according to the definition of $\Delta^h(t)$, there exists at least one $1 \leq l \leq N$, $l \neq h$, such that $\int_s^{s+\xi} a_{lh}(t)dt \geq \epsilon$, i.e., $\mathcal{E}^h(t)$, with edge $\int_s^{s+\xi} a_{lh}(t)dt \geq \epsilon$, is nonempty. Hence, matrices $\int_s^{s+\xi} \Pi^h(t)dt$ are positive definite for all $s \geq t_0$, i.e., there exists a constant $\alpha_1 > 0$ (which depends on ϵ) such that

$$\alpha_1 I \leq \int_s^{s+\xi} (\Pi^h(t) \otimes I_{n_h})dt. \quad (11)$$

By the boundedness of edge weights in Assumption 1, there exists a constant $\alpha_2 > 0$ such that the following inequality holds:

$$\int_s^{s+\xi} (\Pi^h(t) \otimes I_{n_h})dt \leq \alpha_2 I. \quad (12)$$

Thus, from Assumption 5, Lemmas 1 and 2, and the combination of inequalities (11) and (12), it follows that system (9) is globally uniformly exponentially stable.

(Necessity) Based on Lemma 1, the global uniform exponential stability of (8) is equivalent to the following: there exist some constants $\alpha_1 > 0$, $\alpha_2 > 0$, and $\xi > 0$, such that for all $s \geq t_0$ and for each $h = 1, 2, \dots, N$, $\alpha_1 I \leq \int_s^{s+\xi} (\Pi^h(t) \otimes I_{n_h}) dt \leq \alpha_2 I$, which implies that matrices $\int_s^{s+\xi} (\Pi^h(t) \otimes I_{n_h}) dt$ are positive definite. If the time-varying signed interaction graph $\mathcal{G}(t)$ is not jointly (ϵ, T) -connected, i.e., there exists $s^* \geq t_0$, $\forall \epsilon > 0$, $\xi > 0$, such that the graph consisting of a set of edges defined by

$$(i, j) : \int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} a_{ij}(t) dt \geq \epsilon, \quad i, j \in \mathcal{V},$$

is not connected. Then, let $\mathcal{G}_1(t), \mathcal{G}_2(t), \dots, \mathcal{G}_p(t)$, with $p \geq 2$ being the components of $\mathcal{G}(t)$, let \mathcal{V}_I denote the node set of the component $\mathcal{G}_I(t)$ and $|\mathcal{V}_I|$ denote the number of its elements, $I = 1, \dots, p$. The matrix associated with the compact set Γ of $\mathcal{G}(t)$ can then be written as

$$\int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} L(t) dt = \text{diag} \left\{ \int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} L_1(t) dt, \dots, \int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} L_p(t) dt \right\},$$

where $\int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} L_I(t) dt \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{V}_I| \times |\mathcal{V}_I|}$ is related to the Laplacian matrix of component $\mathcal{G}_I(t)$. Correspondingly, for each $h = 1, 2, \dots, N$, matrix $\int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} \Delta^h(t) dt$ can be partitioned as

$$\int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} \Delta^h(t) dt = \text{diag} \left\{ \int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} \Delta_1^h(t) dt, \dots, \int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} \Delta_p^h(t) dt \right\}.$$

Hence, it can be obtained that

$$\int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} \Pi^h(t) dt = \text{diag} \left\{ \int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} \Pi_1^h(t) dt, \dots, \int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} \Pi_p^h(t) dt \right\},$$

where

$$\int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} \Pi_I^h(t) dt = \int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} L_I(t) dt + \int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} \Delta_I^h(t) dt, \quad I = 1, \dots, p.$$

Note that if the number h is included in component J , matrix $\int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} \Delta_I^h(t) dt$ is a zero matrix for $I \neq J$ and thus $\int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} \Pi_I^h(t) dt = \int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} L_I(t) dt$, $I, J = 1, \dots, p$. This, together with the fact that zero is an eigenvalue of $\int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} L_I(t) dt$, implies that zero is an eigenvalue of $\int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} \Pi_I^h(t) dt$. Such a case implies that zero is an eigenvalue of $\int_{s^*}^{s^*+\xi} \Pi^h(t) dt$. This contradicts the fact that matrices $\int_s^{s+\xi} (\Pi^h(t) \otimes I_{n_h}) dt$ are positive definite for all $s \geq t_0$. This completes the proof. \blacksquare

Remark 5: Two constraints, Assumptions 2 and 5, are introduced to address challenges arising from time-varying signed communication networks. Specifically, the persistent excitation condition in Assumption 2 is introduced to address the time-varying property. This assumption is a technical requirement to ensure exponential convergence of the estimation error dynamics and is widely used in the analysis of continuous-time consensus algorithms under time-varying graphs [29]-[31]. It not only accommodates the temporary absence of communication links over finite intervals [13] but also tolerates the presence of negative edge weights caused by malicious attacks. Hence, it covers a broader range of network uncertainties and enables faster convergence compared to joint connected/connected assumptions, making it more practical and robust for real-world applications. Furthermore, Assumption 5 is proposed to ensure stability of the distributed estimator (5b) over graphs with both positive and negative weighted edges. This assumption guarantees that positive interactions generate convergence at a sufficient rate to overcome the effects of negative interactions. \square

Lemma 4: Suppose that the time-varying signed graph $\mathcal{G}(t)$ satisfies Assumptions 1, 2, and 5. Let $\Phi(\tau, t)$ be the state transition matrix of system (8), and $Q(t)$ be a continuous, bounded, positive definite, and symmetric matrix. Then there exists a continuously differentiable, bounded, positive definite, and symmetric matrix $P(t)$ that satisfies the following differential equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{P}(t) &= P(t)(L(t) \otimes I_n + B(t)) \\ &\quad + (L(t) \otimes I_n + B(t))^T P(t) - Q(t), \quad (13) \\ P(0) &= \int_0^\infty \Phi^T(\tau, 0) Q(\tau) \Phi(\tau, 0) d\tau. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Proof: By Lemma 3, the origin of the system (8) is globally uniformly exponentially stable. Let $\phi(\tau; t, \mathbf{y})$ be the solution of (8) that starts at (t, \mathbf{y}) . Note that $\phi(\tau; t, \mathbf{y}) = \Phi(\tau, t)\mathbf{y}$, and there exist $\gamma_1 > 0$, $\gamma_2 > 0$ such that

$$\|\Phi(\tau, t)\| \leq \gamma_1 e^{-\gamma_2(\tau-t)}, \quad \text{for all } \tau \geq t \geq 0.$$

Note that for any $t, \tau \geq 0$, $\Phi(t, \tau)\Phi(\tau, t) = I_{Nn}$ and

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Phi(\tau, t) = \Phi(\tau, t)(L(t) \otimes I_n + B(t)). \quad (14)$$

According to Theorem 4.12 of [34], $P(t)$ is constructed as:

$$P(t) = \int_t^\infty \Phi^T(\tau, t) Q(\tau) \Phi(\tau, t) d\tau, \quad (15)$$

where $Q(t)$ is an arbitrarily chosen continuous, bounded, positive definite, and symmetric matrix. It is clear that $P(t)$ is symmetric and continuously differentiable, and there exist constants $b_1 > 0$ and $b_2 > 0$ such that

$$0 < b_1 I_{Nn} \leq Q(t) \leq b_2 I_{Nn}, \quad \forall t \geq 0. \quad (16)$$

It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y}^T P(t) \mathbf{y} &= \int_t^\infty \phi^T(\tau; t, \mathbf{y}) Q(\tau) \phi(\tau; t, \mathbf{y}) d\tau \\ &\leq \int_t^\infty b_2 \|\Phi(\tau, t)\|^2 \|\mathbf{y}\|^2 d\tau \\ &\leq \int_t^\infty \gamma_1^2 e^{-2\gamma_2(\tau-t)} d\tau \cdot b_2 \|\mathbf{y}\|^2 = \frac{b_2 \gamma_1^2}{2\gamma_2} \|\mathbf{y}\|^2. \quad (17) \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, since $-(L(t) \otimes I_n + B(t))$ is bounded for all $t \geq 0$, there exists a constant $b_3 > 0$ such that $\|-(L(t) \otimes I_n + B(t))\| \leq b_3$, $\forall t \geq 0$. Hence, the solution $\phi(\tau; t, \mathbf{y})$ satisfies

$$\|\phi(\tau; t, \mathbf{y})\|^2 \geq \|\mathbf{y}\|^2 e^{-2b_3(\tau-t)}.$$

Then, it can be derived that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y}^T P(t) \mathbf{y} &\geq \int_t^\infty b_1 \|\phi(\tau; t, \mathbf{y})\|^2 d\tau \\ &\geq \int_t^\infty e^{-2b_3(\tau-t)} d\tau \cdot b_1 \|\mathbf{y}\|^2 = \frac{b_1}{2b_3} \|\mathbf{y}\|^2. \quad (18) \end{aligned}$$

Let $c_1 := \frac{b_1}{2b_3}$ and $c_2 := \frac{b_2 \gamma_1^2}{2\gamma_2}$. It follows that

$$c_1 \|\mathbf{y}\|^2 \leq \mathbf{y}^T P(t) \mathbf{y} \leq c_2 \|\mathbf{y}\|^2, \quad (19)$$

which implies that $P(t)$ is positive definite and bounded. Thus, there exists a constant $c_3 > 0$ such that

$$\|P(t)\| \leq c_3 \quad \text{for all } t \geq 0. \quad (20)$$

Moreover, according to equations (14) and (15), it can be verified that

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{P}(t) &= \int_t^\infty \Phi^T(\tau, t) Q(\tau) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Phi(\tau, t) \right) d\tau \\ &\quad + \int_t^\infty \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Phi^T(\tau, t) \right) Q(\tau) \Phi(\tau, t) d\tau - Q(t) \\ &= P(t)(L(t) \otimes I_n + B(t)) \\ &\quad + (L(t) \otimes I_n + B(t))^T P(t) - Q(t).\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \blacksquare

B. Exponential Convergence Analysis for Nash Equilibrium

To facilitate the subsequent analysis, define the errors as $\mathbf{y}_e := \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x}$, $\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^*$, where \mathbf{x}^* is the Nash equilibrium. Then, based on (5a)-(5b), we have

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\mathbf{y}}_e &= \dot{\mathbf{y}} - \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \dot{\mathbf{x}} \\ &= -((L(t) \otimes I_n + B(t))\mathbf{y} - B(t)(\mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x})) \\ &\quad - \mathbf{1}_N \otimes (-\zeta \bar{\mathbf{k}}\Theta(\mathbf{y})) \\ &= -(L(t) \otimes I_n + B(t))\mathbf{y}_e \\ &\quad + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes (\zeta \bar{\mathbf{k}}\Theta(\mathbf{y}_e + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x}^* + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{e})),\end{aligned}\quad (21)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\mathbf{e}} &= \dot{\mathbf{x}} \\ &= -\zeta \bar{\mathbf{k}}\Theta(\mathbf{y}_e + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x}^* + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{e}).\end{aligned}\quad (22)$$

Theorem 1: Suppose Assumptions 1-5 hold, and the players involved in game (2) under a time-varying signed communication network update their strategies according to (5a)-(5b). Then, there exists a constant ζ^* defined by

$$\zeta^* = \frac{4c(1-c)\gamma b_1}{\Xi}, \quad (23)$$

such that, for $0 < \zeta < \zeta^*$, the equilibrium $(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x}^*)$ is globally uniformly exponentially stable, where $\Xi := 8c(1-c)\gamma \tilde{k} M c_3 + 4(1-c)^2 \tilde{k}^2 M^2 c_3^2 + 4c(1-c)\tilde{k} c_3 M^2 + c^2 M^2$, $c \in (0, 1)$, $\gamma > 0$, $b_1 > 0$, $c_3 > 0$, $M > 0$ are constants, and $\tilde{k} = \sqrt{N} \|\bar{\mathbf{k}}\|$. \square

Proof: Consider the Lyapunov candidate function

$$V(\mathbf{z}, t) = cW_1(\mathbf{e}) + (1-c)\mathbf{y}_e^T P(t)\mathbf{y}_e, \quad (24)$$

where $\mathbf{z} := [\mathbf{e}^T, \mathbf{y}_e^T]^T$, $W_1(\mathbf{e}) = \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{e}^T \bar{\mathbf{k}}^{-1} \mathbf{e}$, and $P(t)$ is defined in (15). Let $k_{\min} = \min\{1/(2\tilde{k}_i), i \in \mathcal{V}\}$ and $k_{\max} = \max\{1/(2\tilde{k}_i), i \in \mathcal{V}\}$, it can be derived that

$$\omega_1 \|\mathbf{z}\|^2 \leq V(\mathbf{z}, t) \leq \omega_2 \|\mathbf{z}\|^2, \quad (25)$$

where $\omega_1 = \min\{ck_{\min}, (1-c)c_1\}$ and $\omega_2 = \max\{ck_{\max}, (1-c)c_2\}$. The derivative of $V(\mathbf{z}, t)$ along systems (21) and (22) is derived as follows:

$$\dot{V}(\mathbf{z}, t) = c\dot{W}_1(\mathbf{e}) + (1-c)\frac{d}{dt}(\mathbf{y}_e^T P(t)\mathbf{y}_e). \quad (26)$$

It is verified that under Assumption 3, it holds that $\|\Theta(\mathbf{y}) - \Theta(\mathbf{y}')\| \leq M\|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}'\|$, $\forall \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{y}' \in \mathbb{R}^{Nn}$, and $\Theta(\mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x}) = F(\mathbf{x})$. Using Assumptions 3 and 4, it can be deduced that

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{W}_1(\mathbf{e}) &= -\zeta \mathbf{e}^T \Theta(\mathbf{y}) \\ &= -\zeta \mathbf{e}^T F(\mathbf{x}) - \zeta \mathbf{e}^T (\Theta(\mathbf{y}) - F(\mathbf{x})) \\ &= -\zeta \mathbf{e}^T (F(\mathbf{x}) - F(\mathbf{x}^*)) - \zeta \mathbf{e}^T (\Theta(\mathbf{y}) - F(\mathbf{x})) \\ &\leq -\zeta \gamma \|\mathbf{e}\|^2 + \zeta M \|\mathbf{e}\| \|\mathbf{y}_e\|.\end{aligned}\quad (27)$$

Also, note that

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d}{dt}(\mathbf{y}_e^T P(t)\mathbf{y}_e) &= \dot{\mathbf{y}}_e^T P(t)\mathbf{y}_e + \mathbf{y}_e^T P(t)\dot{\mathbf{y}}_e + \mathbf{y}_e^T \dot{P}(t)\mathbf{y}_e \\ &= \mathbf{y}_e^T [-P(t)(L(t) \otimes I_n + B(t)) - (L(t) \otimes I_n + B(t))^T P(t) \\ &\quad + \dot{P}(t)]\mathbf{y}_e + \mathbf{y}_e^T P(t)[\mathbf{1}_N \otimes (\zeta \bar{\mathbf{k}}\Theta(\mathbf{y}_e + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x}^* + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{e}))] \\ &\quad + [\mathbf{1}_N \otimes (\zeta \bar{\mathbf{k}}\Theta(\mathbf{y}_e + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x}^* + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{e}))]^T P(t)\mathbf{y}_e \\ &= -\mathbf{y}_e^T Q(t)\mathbf{y}_e + \mathbf{y}_e^T P(t)[\mathbf{1}_N \otimes (\zeta \bar{\mathbf{k}}\Theta(\mathbf{y}_e + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x}^* + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{e}))] \\ &\quad + [\mathbf{1}_N \otimes (\zeta \bar{\mathbf{k}}\Theta(\mathbf{y}_e + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x}^* + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{e}))]^T P(t)\mathbf{y}_e.\end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned}\|\Theta(\mathbf{y}_e + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x}^* + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{e})\| &= \|\Theta(\mathbf{y}_e + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x})\| \\ &= \|\Theta(\mathbf{y}_e + \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x}) - \Theta(\mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x}) + F(\mathbf{x}) - F(\mathbf{x}^*)\| \\ &\leq M(\|\mathbf{y}_e\| + \|\mathbf{e}\|),\end{aligned}$$

together with (16) and (20), it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d}{dt}(\mathbf{y}_e^T P(t)\mathbf{y}_e) &\leq -\mathbf{y}_e^T Q(t)\mathbf{y}_e + 2\zeta M \sqrt{N} \|\bar{\mathbf{k}}\| \cdot \|\mathbf{y}_e\| \cdot \|P(t)\| \cdot (\|\mathbf{y}_e\| + \|\mathbf{e}\|) \\ &\leq -b_1 \|\mathbf{y}_e\|^2 + 2\zeta M \tilde{k} c_3 \|\mathbf{y}_e\|^2 + 2\zeta M \tilde{k} c_3 \|\mathbf{y}_e\| \|\mathbf{e}\|.\end{aligned}\quad (28)$$

Substituting (27) and (28) into (26) gives

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{V}(\mathbf{z}, t) &\leq -c\zeta\gamma\|\mathbf{e}\|^2 - (1-c)b_1\|\mathbf{y}_e\|^2 \\ &\quad + c\zeta M\|\mathbf{e}\|\|\mathbf{y}_e\| + 2(1-c)\zeta M\tilde{k}c_3\|\mathbf{e}\|\|\mathbf{y}_e\| \\ &\quad + 2(1-c)\zeta M\tilde{k}c_3\|\mathbf{y}_e\|^2 \\ &= -\zeta[\|\mathbf{e}\| \ \|\mathbf{y}_e\|] B \begin{bmatrix} \|\mathbf{e}\| \\ \|\mathbf{y}_e\| \end{bmatrix} \\ &\leq -\zeta\lambda_{\min}(B)\|\mathbf{z}\|^2,\end{aligned}\quad (29)$$

where

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} c\gamma & -\frac{cM}{2} - (1-c)M\tilde{k}c_3 \\ -\frac{cM}{2} - (1-c)M\tilde{k}c_3 & (1-c)\left(\frac{b_1}{\zeta} - 2M\tilde{k}c_3\right) \end{bmatrix}.$$

Let ζ^* determined by (23), then for all $0 < \zeta < \zeta^*$, matrix B is positive definite. According to equations (25) and (29), it can be derived that

$$\|\mathbf{z}(t)\| \leq \sqrt{\frac{\omega_2}{\omega_1}} e^{-\frac{\zeta\lambda_{\min}(B)}{2\omega_2}t} \|\mathbf{z}(0)\|,$$

which implies that $\|\mathbf{e}\|, \|\mathbf{y}_e\|$ exponentially converge to zero as $t \rightarrow \infty$, i.e., (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) exponentially converges to $(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{x}^*)$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. This completes the proof. \blacksquare

Remark 6: This work provides an analytical framework for Nash equilibrium seeking over time-varying signed networks. The framework is both comprehensive and widely applicable due to the following two reasons: first, it shares a structural similarity with the well-established Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm introduced in reference [9]; second, its theoretical foundation follows the persistent excitation condition proposed in references [29]-[31], which is well-established in the study of continuous-time consensus dynamics with switching interaction graphs. Additionally, taking the emergence of negative edges and the disappearance of existing positive edges as forms of network faults or adversarial attacks on the network, Assumptions 1, 2, and 5 provide sufficient conditions for the passive fault tolerance of communication networks. \square

Remark 7: There are two key technical points in integrating uniform complete observability of linear time-varying systems into the Nash equilibrium seeking process. The first one is the *exponential stability analysis of the distributed estimator (Lemma 3)*: By leveraging the uniform complete observability of linear time-varying systems,

we established the exponential stability of the error dynamics in the distributed estimator used within the Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm. The imposed constraints (Assumptions 2 and 5) on time-varying signed networks are designed to ensure that the linear time-varying system satisfies a uniform complete observability condition. This enables each player to accurately estimate the strategies of others, while also offering analytical tools to address faulty processes occurring in distributed communication among agents during multi-agent games. The second point is the *alternative differential equation for Lyapunov analysis (Lemma 4)*: Lemma 4 provides an alternative differential equation (13) to replace the algebraic Lyapunov equation $P_1(L_1 \otimes I_n + B_1) + (L_1 \otimes I_n + B_1)^T P_1 = Q_1$ determined by the Hurwitz matrix $-(L_1 \otimes I_n + B_1)$. This differential equation enables the construction of a Lyapunov function, facilitating stability analysis and ensuring the convergence of players' strategies to the Nash equilibrium. \square

IV. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

This section presents an example illustrating the application of the extended distributed Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm to a connectivity control game [3], demonstrating the effectiveness of our results.

Example: Consider a network of 5 mobile sensors (players) equipped with the time-varying signed communication graph $\mathcal{G}_{\sigma(t)}(t)$, which is defined by the following switching signal $\sigma(t)$:

$$\sigma(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } 2s \leq t < 2s + 0.5, \\ 2, & \text{if } 2s + 0.5 \leq t < 2s + 1, \\ 3, & \text{if } 2s + 1 \leq t < 2s + 2, \end{cases}$$

where $s = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. The three graphs $\mathcal{G}_i(t)$ are depicted in Figure 1. The functions $g_1(t)$ and $g_2(t)$ are given by: $g_1(t) = \sin(\pi t) * \hat{f}_1(t) + \frac{1}{[t+1]^{0.2}} * \hat{f}_1(t)$, $g_2(t) = -\sin(\pi t) * \hat{f}_2(t) - 0.5 * \frac{1}{[t+1]^{0.3}} * \hat{f}_2(t)$, where $[\cdot]$ denotes the greatest integer function, and $\hat{f}_1(t)$, $\hat{f}_2(t)$ are periodic functions defined by: $\hat{f}_1(t) = 1$ if $t \in [2s, 2s + 1)$ and $\hat{f}_1(t) = 0$, otherwise; $\hat{f}_2(t) = 1 - \hat{f}_1(t)$. Note that Assumptions 1, 2, and 5 hold. Each sensor attempts to find a balance between its local and global objectives, and the cost function of sensor i is defined as: $J_i(\mathbf{x}) = f_i^c(x_i) + f_i^g(\mathbf{x})$, where $f_i^c(x_i) = x_i^T R_i x_i + x_i^T r_i + b_i$ is the local objective function and $f_i^g(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{l \in \mathcal{N}_i^p} \tilde{c}_{il} \|x_i - x_l\|^2$ is the global objective function, with \mathcal{N}_i^p denoting the physical neighbor set of sensor i , and $x_i = [x_{i1}, x_{i2}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$ denoting the position of sensor i .

Figure 1. Time-varying communication graph $\mathcal{G}_{\sigma(t)}(t)$ among 5 players, where the dashed line represents the edge weight as a time-varying function, the red line represents negative weights, and the black line represents positive weights.

Consider $R_i = \begin{bmatrix} i & 0 \\ 0 & i \end{bmatrix}$, $r_i = [i, i]^T$, $b_i = i$, $f_1^g(\mathbf{x}) = \|x_1 - x_2\|^2$, $f_2^g(\mathbf{x}) = \|x_2 - x_3\|^2$, $f_3^g(\mathbf{x}) = \|x_3 - x_2\|^2$, $f_4^g(\mathbf{x}) = \|x_4 - x_2\|^2 + \|x_4 - x_5\|^2$, $f_5^g(\mathbf{x}) = \|x_5 - x_1\|^2$. We can calculate the unique Nash equilibrium in this game: $x_{i1}^* = -0.5$, $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$, $l = 1, 2$. Randomly set the initial conditions to be $\mathbf{x}(0) = [-10, 2, -3, -8, -5, 6, 0, -8, -1, 10]^T$. Figure 2a shows the evolution of players' strategies generated by the proposed seeking strategy (4a)-(4b), while Figure 2b shows the players' estimates on all

players' strategies. Finally, from Figure 2c, it can be concluded that, despite the communication network being time-varying and signed, the sensors' positions converge to the Nash equilibrium using the proposed extended distributed Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm.

Figure 2a. Players' strategies $x_i(t)$, $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$.

Figure 2b. Player i 's estimates on the players' action $y_{ij}(t)$, $j \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$.

Figure 2c. Trajectories of the sensors' positions.

V. CONCLUSION

This work develops a distributed Nash equilibrium seeking algorithm that integrates pseudogradient dynamics and a distributed estimator to solve multi-agent game problems under time-varying signed communication networks. Exponential stability of the error dynamics of the distributed estimator is achieved if and only if the joint (ϵ, T) -connectivity and the negative-link assumption are satisfied by the time-varying signed graphs. This result contributes to the construction of the Lyapunov function candidate for analyzing the exponential stability of the Nash equilibrium driven by the seeking algorithm. The validity of the proposed algorithm is illustrated through a practical application example.

While the conditions proposed in this work suggest that the adverse effects of negative interactions in networks can be mitigated by positive interactions, the specific method of adjusting positive connection weights to counteract these effects has not been explored. This perspective is crucial for understanding how to adjust players' strategies when faced with sudden shifts from cooperative to non-cooperative behavior in games, offering valuable insights for our future research. Another future direction of research is to extend the algorithm to time-varying directed signed graphs. The main challenges involve: (i) the unclear extension of graph-theoretical methods from undirected to directed graphs, due to the added complexity of directionality; and (ii) the difficulty of developing new analytical tools to manage the complexity of node relationships and matrix properties in directed graphs.

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